

REPORT

A.2.2.4: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for halogenated volatile organic compounds with TD-GC/MS/FID using the static standards produced in A1.1.3.

This report was written by:

Sandra Hultmark RISE sandra.hultmark@ri.se

Karine Arrhenius RISE karine.arrhenius@ri.se

Table of Contents

1. INTRODUCTION	3
2. MATERIALS AND METHODS	3
3. VALIDATION	3
<i>General overview</i>	<i>3</i>
<i>Selectivity</i>	<i>5</i>
<i>Limit of detection and quantification</i>	<i>7</i>
<i>Working range and linearity</i>	<i>8</i>
<i>Trueness, Bias</i>	<i>13</i>
<i>Precision</i>	<i>14</i>
<i>Measurement uncertainties</i>	<i>19</i>
4. CONCLUSIONS	19
5. REFERENCES	19

1. Introduction

The BiometCAP project is developing a performance assessment protocol (A2.1.4) for evaluating instruments and methods used for biomethane conformity assessment. Here, this performance assessment protocol was tested and validated using the method ISO 2620:2024 for the determination of halogenated volatile organic compounds in biogas/biomethane matrices. The method is based on thermal desorption followed by gas chromatography with a mass spectrometer and a flame ionization detector (TD-GC/MS-FID). The validation parameters evaluated here were selectivity, limit of detection and quantification, working range and linearity, trueness/bias, and precision. Using these results, the measurement uncertainty was calculated for each component.

2. Materials and methods

The TD-GC/MS-FID instrument was operated in electron impact mode with standard conditions, including an electron energy of 70 eV and a mass scan range from 29 to 300 amu. The analysis utilized a BPX5 column measuring 50 m x 32 mm ID x 1 µm with 5% phenylpolysilphenylene siloxane. Sorbent tubes underwent a two-step thermal desorption process using a Markes TD100 desorber by first heating the tubes to 275 °C for seven minutes to release the adsorbed species. These substances were then focused at -10 °C in a cold trap containing graphitized carbon before being rapidly heated to 300 °C for separation on the GC column. The column effluent was split for detection and quantification, with one stream passing through a flame ionization detector (FID) and the other through a mass spectrometer (MS).

A reference mixture produced by VSL in methane as part of activity A1.1.3 containing 0.0526 µmol/mol of 1,2-dichloropropane, 0.0695 µmol/mol of 1,1,2-trichloroethane, 0.05 µmol/mol of dichloromethane, 0.0524 µmol/mol of tetrachloroethylene and 0.0528 µmol/mol of trichloroethylene was used for the validation.

3. Validation

General overview

The planning steps of the general procedure for determining the performance characteristics of the instrument taken from the protocol developed in A2.1.4 are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Four steps with general procedure for determination of the performance characteristics.

Step	Phase	Description	Results
1	Planning	Specify the components required to be measured by the instrument and the measurement range for each over which the instrument shall be evaluated.	Validation will be done for Dichloromethane, Trichloromethane, 1,2-dichloropropane, 1,1,2-dichloroethane and Tetrachloroethylene.
2	Planning	Establish the functional descriptions of the response functions assumed by the instrument for each specified component.	The response should be linear.
3	Planning	Specify a set of reference gas mixtures (calibration gases) with compositions covering all ranges for all components specified in step 1.	Only one gas mixture will be used: VSL mixture prepared as part of A1.1.3. A reference solution of all the siloxanes in diethylether was used for the calibration.
4	Planning	Establish the composition and uncertainty of the calibration gas mixture(s) to be used for routine calibration of the instrument.	Around 0.05 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ per compounds

The extent of the performance characteristic validation taken from the protocol designed in A2.1.4 is summarised for this application in Table 2.

Table 2. Extent of validation.

Performance characteristic	Analytical application		
	Component identification	Component detection	Component quantification
Selectivity	x	x	x
Limit of detection		x	
Limit of quantification			x
Working range			x
Trueness			x
Precision			x
Rise time			Not applicable
Memory effect and fall time			Not applicable

Based on previous experiences, for this method, the targeted relative within-laboratory reproducibility, $u(R_w)$, is set at 2.5 % and the targeted relative bias, $u(\text{bias})$, is set at 5%.

Selectivity

Protocol: To perform the selectivity evaluation, use a reference material containing both the analyte of interest and other components that are expected to be present within the biomethane samples.

Here we used a reference biogas sample containing both the analyte of interest and other components. The selectivity of the method was investigated by studying its ability to measure the analyte of interest in the sample where interferences have been introduced. The method should be optimized to avoid co-elution of the analyte of interest and the other components present in the sample. With the selected GC parameters for this method and with an FID detector, the following chromatogram was obtained for a biogas sample from a plant digesting food waste (figure 1). As can be seen in the figure, Dichloromethane eluates close to cyclopentyl acetylene.

Figure 1. The TD-GC using FID detector shows that Dichloromethane eluates close to cyclopentyl acetylene.

Resolution was calculated according to this equation [1]:

$$\frac{t_{R2} - t_{R1}}{\frac{1}{2}(W_1 + W_2)}$$

Where t_{R2} , t_{R1} are retention time for each peak and W_1 , W_2 are width of each peak. A resolution of 1.5 or more occurs when the signal returns to its baseline between two peaks, indicating good separation. Dichloromethane eluate close to cyclopentyl acetylene and calculation of the peak resolution gives a value of 1.2, indicating a slight overlap between peaks and poor resolution.

The same sample with an MS detector provides a good resolution of the chromatogram, see figure 2.

Limit of detection and quantification

Protocol: the LOD and LOQ are calculated in one of two ways: via replicate measurements of blank samples, or via replicate measurements of test samples with a suitably low amount fraction of the analyte.

In this case, the method “replicate measurements of test samples with a suitably low amount fraction of the analyte” was chosen. The limit of detection and quantification (LOD and LOQ) for Dichloromethane, Trichloromethane, 1,2-dichloropropane, 1,1,2-dichloroethane and Tetrachloroethylene were calculated with a Signal-to-Noise (S/N) approach. The S/N ratio is determined by comparing signals from samples with known low amount of analyte with those of blank samples. LOD and LOQ is the determination of the minimum amount at which the analyte can be confidently detected and quantified. Here, the LOD is determined for S/N = 3 and the LOQ for S/N = 10. The results are presented in Table 3. The results show that the method is highly sensitive and can be used to analyze samples with low amount fractions of HVOCs.

Table 3. Calculated limits of detection and quantification for HVOCs.

Compounds	Target amount ng	Noise	Signal	S/N at target amount	LOD ng (S/N = 3)	LOQ ng (S/N = 10)
Dichloromethane MS	12	1200	16700	14	2.6	8.8
Trichloroethylene MS	20	800	29640	37	1.6	5.4
1,2-dichloropropane MS	17	800	25700	32	1.6	5.4
1,1,2-trichloroethane MS	27	900	39500	44	1.8	6.1
Tetrachloroethylene MS	25	1000	42250	42	1.8	6.0
Dichloromethane FID	12	80	2300	29	1.3	4.3
Trichloroethylene FID	20	80	5050	63	1.0	3.2
1,2-dichloropropane FID	17	80	7850	98	0.5	1.8
1,1,2-dichloroethane FID	27	80	7785	97	0.8	2.8
Tetrachloroethylene FID	25	100	6270	63	1.2	4.0

Working range and linearity

Protocol: To assess the instrument working range:

- 1) Identify the **range of interest** (recommended to span $\pm 10\%$ of the expected calibration range) and measure blanks and calibration standards at 6 - 10 amount fractions spread evenly across this range: 10 to 500 ng.
- 2) Plot response against amount fraction and visually examine plot to identify the approximate **linear range**.
- 3) To quantify linearity over the identified **linear range**, measure blanks and calibration standards at 6 - 10 amount fractions spread evenly across the linear range.
- 4) Plot response (y axis) against amount fraction (x axis) and calculate appropriate regression statistics. Plot the residuals (difference in observed y value and predicted by the straight line fit). Random distribution around zero confirms linearity.

Dichloromethane

The linearity was assessed by analyzing 7 different amounts in nanograms (ng) of Dichloromethane. Results for Dichloromethane measured in the range 12 to 61 ng are shown in Figure 2. As illustrated in Figure 2, the correlation coefficient for Dichloromethane measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 12 to 61 ng.

Figure 2. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 3).

Figure 3. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

Trichloroethylene

The linearity was assessed by analyzing seven different amounts in nanograms (ng) of Trichloroethylene. Results for Trichloroethylene measured in the range 20 to 100 ng are shown in Figure 4. As illustrated in Figure 4, the correlation coefficient for Trichloroethylene measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 20 to 100 ng.

Figure 4. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residual is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 5).

Figure 5. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

1,2-dichloropropane

The linearity was assessed by analyzing seven different amounts in nanograms (ng) of 1,2-dichloropropane. Results for 1,2-dichloropropane measured in the range 17 to 86 ng are shown in Figure 6. As illustrated in Figure 6, the correlation coefficient for 1,2-dichloropropane measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 17 to 86 ng.

Figure 6. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residual is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 7).

Figure 7. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

1,1,2-trichloroethane

The linearity was assessed by analyzing seven different amounts in nanograms (ng) of 1,1,2-trichloroethane. Results for 1,1,2-trichloroethane measured in the range 27 to 134 ng are shown in Figure 8. As illustrated in Figure 8, the correlation coefficient for 1,1,2-trichloroethane measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 27 to 134 ng.

Figure 8. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 9).

Figure 9. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

Tetrachloroethylene

The linearity was assessed by analyzing seven different amounts in nanograms (ng) of Tetrachloroethylene. Results for Tetrachloroethylene measured in the range 25 to 126 ng are shown in Figure 10. As illustrated in Figure 10, the correlation coefficient for Tetrachloroethylene measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 25 to 126 ng.

Figure 10. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 11).

Figure 11. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

Trueness, Bias

Protocol, approach 1: evaluation against a reference material: compare mean measured value, with the reference value for the reference material. Calculate bias, relative bias, or the relative recovery (apparent recovery)

The differences between the calculated concentrations and the expected concentrations are presented in Table 4. Using this result, the standard deviation of the measured concentration, S_{RW} , was calculated to be 1.8 %. Taking into account the uncertainty of the reference standard, the total bias, $u(\text{bias})$, was calculated to be 4.11% which is in good agreement with the targeted value of 5%.

Table 4. Bias calculated for Dichloromethane with MS.

Results $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	Expected results, $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	Bias	Relative Bias
169	176	-7	-4
172	176	-4	-2
176	176	0	0
166	176	-10	-6
170	176	-6	-4
	Mean	-5	-3

Precision

Protocol: To evaluate repeatability measure the analyte(s) of interest within a reference material at various concentrations spread across the working range using the same method. Obtain at least 10 replicate measurements and calculate the standard deviation and relative standard deviation.

Precision was assessed by measuring 10 duplicates of Dichloromethane, Trichloroethylene, 1,2-dichloropropane, 1,1,2-trichloroethane and Tetrachloroethylene at varying quantities using TD-GC-MS/FID on several days. Standard deviation, as well as relative standard deviation, were determined and the pooled standard deviation was calculated. The results are presented in Table 5-12.

Table 5. Estimation of the intermediate precision for Dichloromethane using GC-FID.

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240315)	1.57	1.57	0.00	0.07
2 (240315)	2.03	2.00	0.02	0.99
3 (240315)	3.05	3.02	0.02	0.58
4 (240311)	0.44	0.46	0.02	3.58
5 (240311)	1.09	1.07	0.02	1.39
6 (240311)	2.30	2.31	0.01	0.47
7 (240308)	1.13	1.07	0.05	4.23
8 (240308)	1.68	1.71	0.02	1.02
9(240308)	2.51	2.48	0.02	0.62
10(240308)	3.29	3.33	0.03	0.78
			Rel STD	1.7
			Sr % pooled	1.8

Table 6. Estimation of the intermediate precision for Dichloromethane using GC-MS

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240315)	3.37	3.41	0.03	0.77
2 (240315)	4.26	4.35	0.06	1.48
3 (240315)	6.56	6.75	0.13	2.01

4 (240311)	1.13	1.14	0.01	0.68
5 (240311)	2.22	2.27	0.04	1.60
6 (240311)	4.94	4.98	0.03	0.56
7 (240308)	3.94	3.97	0.02	0.55
8 (240308)	6.28	6.19	0.07	1.13
9 (240308)	9.05	8.78	0.19	2.12
10(240308)	2.67	2.50	0.12	4.50
			Rel STD	1.9
			Sr % pooled	1.9

Table 7. Estimation of the intermediate precision for Trichloroethylene using GC-FID.

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240315)	3.68	3.67	0.00	0.10
2 (240315)	4.71	4.75	0.03	0.53
3 (240315)	7.38	7.25	0.09	1.26
4 (240311)	1.24	1.23	0.00	0.21
5 (240311)	2.37	2.35	0.01	0.50
6 (240311)	5.28	5.34	0.04	0.84
7 (240308)	2.72	2.63	0.06	2.29
8 (240308)	4.06	4.01	0.03	0.83
9 (240308)	6.76	6.83	0.05	0.66
10(240308)	8.92	9.18	0.18	2.03
			Rel STD	1.3
			Sr % pooled	1.2

Table 8. Estimation of the intermediate precision for Trichloroethylene using GC-MS

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240315)	3.21	3.18	0.02	0.72
2 (240315)	4.13	4.03	0.07	1.80
3 (240315)	6.30	6.25	0.03	0.53
4 (240311)	1.24	1.19	0.03	2.87
5 (240311)	2.43	2.40	0.02	0.85

6 (240311)	5.28	5.28	0.00	0.04
7 (240308)	3.10	3.06	0.02	0.75
8 (240308)	4.55	4.55	0.00	0.07
9 (240308)	7.63	7.75	0.08	1.05
10(240308)	10.55	10.64	0.06	0.57
			Rel STD	1.2
			Sr % pooled	1.2

Table 9. Estimation of the intermediate precision for 1,2-dichloropropane using GC-FID.

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240315)	3.92	3.90	0.01	0.28
2 (240315)	5.43	5.45	0.01	0.21
3 (240315)	7.16	7.26	0.07	0.92
4 (240315)	11.09	10.93	0.12	1.05
5 (240311)	1.84	1.86	0.02	0.84
6 (240311)	3.59	3.63	0.03	0.82
7 (240311)	8.00	7.98	0.01	0.17
8 (240308)	6.16	6.08	0.06	0.99
9 (240308)	9.81	10.07	0.18	1.86
10(240308)	13.64	13.44	0.14	1.06
			Rel STD	1.0
			Sr % pooled	0.9

Table 10. Estimation of the intermediate precision for 1,2-dichloropropane using GC-MS

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240315)	2.40	2.35	0.04	1.48
2 (240315)	3.20	3.11	0.07	2.13
3 (240315)	4.04	4.11	0.05	1.18
4 (240315)	6.34	6.46	0.09	1.36
5 (240311)	1.11	1.11	0.00	0.02
6 (240311)	2.23	2.20	0.02	1.12
7 (240311)	4.91	4.98	0.05	0.96

8 (240308)	3.91	3.87	0.03	0.74
9 (240308)	6.58	6.62	0.02	0.37
10(240308)	9.27	9.26	0.01	0.07
			Rel STD	1.2
			Sr % pooled	1.1

Table 11. Estimation of the intermediate precision for 1,1,2-trichloroethane using GC-FID.

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240315)	3.93	3.94	0.01	0.22
2 (240315)	5.48	5.50	0.02	0.36
3 (240315)	7.21	7.17	0.03	0.36
4 (240315)	11.34	11.04	0.21	1.88
5 (240311)	3.15	3.19	0.02	0.72
6 (240311)	6.87	6.86	0.01	0.20
7 (240308)	4.14	4.13	0.01	0.18
8 (240308)	6.24	6.10	0.10	1.61
9 (240308)	8.26	8.28	0.01	0.15
10(240308)	10.24	10.25	0.01	0.09
			Rel STD	0.7
			Sr % pooled	0.9

Table 12. Estimation of the intermediate precision for 1,1,2-trichloroethane using GC-MS

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240315)	3.32	3.30	0.01	0.41
2 (240315)	4.54	4.40	0.10	2.13
3 (240315)	5.62	5.65	0.02	0.39
4 (240315)	8.74	8.90	0.11	1.24
5 (240311)	2.69	2.71	0.01	0.36
6 (240311)	5.99	5.94	0.04	0.62
7 (240308)	3.96	3.80	0.11	2.90
8 (240308)	5.75	5.77	0.02	0.33
9 (240308)	7.53	7.67	0.10	1.27
10(240308)	9.89	9.99	0.07	0.74

			Rel STD	1.3
			Sr % pooled	1.4

Table 11. Estimation of the intermediate precision for Tetrachloroethylene using GC-FID.

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240315)	4.56	4.53	0.02	0.48
2 (240315)	5.78	5.81	0.02	0.33
3 (240315)	9.29	9.20	0.06	0.69
4 (240311)	1.45	1.42	0.02	1.37
5 (240311)	2.88	2.92	0.02	0.85
6 (240311)	6.35	6.33	0.01	0.16
7 (240308)	3.32	3.36	0.02	0.71
8 (240308)	4.92	5.00	0.06	1.17
9 (240308)	6.66	6.69	0.02	0.34
10(240308)	11.78	11.93	0.11	0.90
			Rel STD	0.9
			Sr % pooled	0.8

Table 12. Estimation of the intermediate precision for Tetrachloroethylene using GC-MS

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240315)	4.10	4.06	0.03	0.74
2 (240315)	5.25	5.09	0.11	2.18
3 (240315)	7.85	8.05	0.15	1.83
4 (240311)	1.62	1.61	0.00	0.30
5 (240311)	3.14	3.12	0.02	0.51
6 (240311)	6.73	6.84	0.08	1.16
7 (240308)	4.06	3.99	0.05	1.29
8 (240308)	5.98	5.93	0.04	0.66
9 (240308)	7.79	7.97	0.13	1.66
10(240308)	13.89	13.69	0.14	1.01
			Rel STD	1.4
			Sr % pooled	1.3

The measured pooled standard deviations, S_r , varies between 0.8 to 1.9 %. Taking into account, the contribution of control samples (here toluene), the within-laboratory reproducibility, $u(R_w)$, is evaluated to be 2.65% for Dichloromethane in MS, a bit higher than the targeted value of 2.5%.

Measurement uncertainties

The expanded uncertainty ($k=2$) for L2 was calculated using the software MUKit. In general, measurement uncertainty of 10% or less are considered reliable. The calculations show that the measurement uncertainty is 10% and the method is therefore reliable (Table 13).

Table 13. Within-laboratory reproducibility, method biases and expanded uncertainties from the TD-GC-MS/FID system for dichloromethane.

Compounds	$u(R_w)$ rel.	$u(\text{bias})$ rel.	$U = 2u_c$
Dichloromethane	2.65%	4.11%	10%

4. Conclusions

The validation of the method ISO 2620:2024 for halogenated volatile organic compounds was performed according to the performance assessment protocol written in (A2.1.4). However, only two CRM were used compared to three recommended in the protocol for a linear regression, but the method had previously been validated using five different CRM.

ISO 2620:2024 is therefore found to be fit-for-purpose, reliable and highly sensitive. As the working range is at least 10 to 100 ng, it can be used to analyze samples with amount fractions of halogenated volatile organic compounds from 10 nmol/mol to 1 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ (using volumes of 70 to 350 ml per tube).

5. References

[1] Shimadzu, <https://www.shimadzu.com/an/service-support/technical-support/analysis-basics/basic/resol-1.html>